

IMPROVING BRAIN TUMOR CLASSIFICATION ON MRI USING MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH AND FUZZY SEGMENTATION

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I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract— The project proposes an improve method of MRI brain image classification and image segmentation approach. It is automatic support system for stage classification using learning machine and to detect Brain Tumor through spatial fuzzy clustering methods for bio medical application. Automated classification and detection of tumors in different medical images is motivated by the necessity of high accuracy when dealing with a human life. The detection of the Brain Tumor is a challenging problem, due to the structure of the Tumor cells. This project presents a segmentation method, spatial fuzzy clustering algorithm, for segmenting Magnetic Resonance images to detect the Brain Tumor in its early stages and to analyze anatomical structures. The artificial neural network will be used to classify the stage of Brain Tumor that is benign, malignant or normal. Here Dual Tree CWT multi scale decomposition is used to analysis texture of an image. The segmentation results will be used as a base for a Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) system for early detection of Brain Tumor which will improves the chances of survival for the patient. In brain structure analysis, the tissues which are WM and GM are extracted. Probabilistic Neural Network with radial basis function will be employed to implement an automated Brain Tumor classification. Decision making was performed in two stages: feature extraction using GLCM and the classification using PNN-RBF network. The performance of this classifier was evaluated in terms of training performance and classification accuracies. The simulated results will be shown that classifier and segmentation algorithm provides better accuracy than previous method.

Index Terms—magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Dual Tree Complex Wavelet Transform(DTCWT), Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN), Radial Base Function (RBF).

MAGNETIC resonance imaging (MRI) is a noninvasive technique relevant for planning and monitoring of cancer treatment [1]. Texture analysis can capture important characteristics of an image [5], [6]. With no formal definition, a pattern with randomness and regularity is usually considered a texture. An additional characteristic of texture is busyness, i.e., the degree of mix between randomness and regularity. Texture features describe these properties quantitatively, where emphasis is on the spatial relationship between pixels, rather than on single pixel intensities. By using texture features for tumor classification, the heterogeneity both within the tumor (features) and between tumors (classification) can be investigated [7]. The use of relative measures rather than absolute intensities can make texture features less sensitive to differences in MR protocols and between scanners [2], [8], [9]. One approach to texture analysis is to study the gray level co-occurrence, where a matrix of co-occurring gray level pairs (GLCM) in the image is constructed, from which second-order statistical texture features can be calculated [5]. GLCM texture analysis of medical images is relatively computationally efficient and the GLCM features provide fairly straightforward interpretations [10]. Recently, GLCM based textural features from MRI have been investigated for different types of cancer [11].

Due to overcome some drawbacks, the MRI Brain image Classification and anatomical structure analysis are proposed. This proposal is based on PNN-RBF Network for classification and Spatial Fuzzy clustering for tumor detection. In the past decades, research carried out into brain cancer diagnosis has seen dynamic growth in the number of tasks. Many university centres [19], because brain cancer is spreading among the population of the world that are focused on issues of fact. In the U. S. for example, approximately 3, 000 children are diagnosed with brain tumors. Almost half of the most deadly cancer among children, which die within five years [18].

For negative effects on people affected by cancer diseases have a high burden on the national economy and society as well as a source of suffering for the family formed. To identify a tumor, the patient will undergo several tests. In recent years a great effort of the research in field of medical imaging was focused on brain tumors segmentation. The automatic segmentation has great potential in clinical medicine by freeing physicians from the burden of manual labeling.

In this proposed study a supervised MRI brain image classification and image segmentation approach is implemented. It is automatic support system for stage classification using machine learning and to detect Brain Tumor through spatial fuzzy clustering methods for bio medical application. Even though many techniques are there to detect brain tumor, this proposed method is more helpful to detect tumor in its earlier stage itself.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

a) Gray Level Co-Occurrence

Haralick proposed two steps for texture feature extraction: The first is computing the co-occurrence matrix and The second step is calculating texture feature base on the co-occurrence matrix. This technique is useful in a wide range of image analysis applications from biomedical to remote sensing techniques. One of the defining qualities of texture is the spatial distribution of gray values. The use of statistical features is therefore one of the earliest methods proposed in the image processing literature. Haralick suggested the use of co-occurrence matrix or gray level co-occurrence matrix. It considers the relationship between two neighbouring pixels, the first pixel is known as a reference and the second is known as a neighbour pixel. In statistical texture analysis, texture features are computed from the statistical distribution of observed combinations of intensities at specified positions relative to each other in the image.

Texture is defined as a function of the spatial variation in pixel intensities. According to the number of intensity points (pixels) in each combination, statistics are classified into first order, second order and higher order statistics. Haralick proposed the following texture features: Energy, Contrast, Homogeneity, Entropy

Hence, for each Haralick texture feature, we obtain a co-occurrence matrix. These co-occurrence matrices represent the spatial distribution and the dependence of the grey levels within a local area. Each (i,j) th entry in the matrices, represents the probability of going from one pixel with a grey level of 'i' to another with a grey level of 'j' under a predefined distance and angle. From these matrices, sets of statistical measures are computed, called feature vectors. Second-order statistical texture features can be calculated from the gray level co-occurrence matrix. These features are descriptions of the textures in the original image [5]. Haralick *et al.* [23] suggested 14 different features. As these features are not all independent of each other, it is common practice to select only a few features for analysis.

this study.

First, contrast K is defined as

$$\text{Contrast} = \sum_i \sum_j (i-j)^2 P^2[i,j] \quad (1)$$

Energy, also known as the angular second moment, is simply the sum of squares of all the elements in the GLCM

$$\text{Energy} = \sum_i \sum_j P^2[i,j] \quad (2)$$

Energy measures uniformity, and ranges from zero to unity for a uniform image.

Homogeneity is defined a

$$\text{Homogeneity} = [\sum_i \sum_j P[i,j]] / 1 + |i-j| \quad (3)$$

is a measure of the closeness of the elements in the GLCM to the diagonal. It ranges from zero to one. Homogeneity is unity for a diagonal GLCM, that is, if all pixels in the original image have the same value as their neighbor.

Entropy, It measures image texture randomness, when the space co-occurrence matrix for all values are equal, it achieved the minimum value.

$$\text{Entropy} = \sum_i \sum_j P[i,j] \log P[i,j] \quad (4)$$

b) DTCWT decomposition

An input noisy image will be decomposed into components like textural and structural details using dual tree complex wavelet transform. It is a shift and rotation invariant transform describes the textures and edges in various directions.

DT-CWT decomposes an image into low and high frequency subbands. Low/high frequency subbands are contains coarsest and finest details. It is directionally selective in two and higher dimensions where the high-frequency sub bands in six different directions contribute to the sharpness of the image details. The real and complex band coefficients are utilized and LF's are kept same.

c) Probabilistic Neural Network

The proposed neural network has been used to detect and locate the defect in two cases. The first case was to detect and locate a defect in a two-dimensional sector of the breast model. The location of defect was considered randomly at the centre and in any of the four quadratures. The second case was to detect and locate defect anywhere in the three-dimensional model. The PNN classifier presented good accuracy, very small training time, robustness to weight changes, and negligible retraining time. There are six stages involved in the proposed model which are starting from the data input to output. The first stage is should be the image processing system. Basically in image processing system, image acquisition and image enhancement are the steps that have to do. These two steps are skipped and all the images are collected from available resource. The proposed model requires converting the image into a format capable of being manipulated by the computer. The defect images are converted into matrices form by using MATLAB. Then, the PNN is used to classify the defect images.

The probabilistic neural network was developed by Donald Specht. This network provides a general solution to pattern classification problems by following an approach developed in statistics, called Bayesian Classifiers. PNN is adopted for it has many advantages. Its training speed is many times faster than a BP network.

PNN can Approach a Bayes optimal result under certain easily

met conditions. Additionally, it is robust to noise examples.

Advance hybrid PNN such as done by Georgiadas *et al* aimed to improve brain tumor characterization on MRI by using PNN and nonlinear transformation of textured features.

This method employs a two level hierarchical decision tree discriminate the metastatic brain tumor cases from the gliomas and meningiomas (primary brain tumor) cases. At each level, classification was performed using two different LSFTPNN classifier. LSST-PNN then was compared with the support Vector Machines with Radial Basis Kernel (SVM-RBF) and the

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) classifiers. However, we choose a basic Mat lab PNN for its simple structure and training manner.

Probabilistic Neural Networks (PNN) is a class of neural networks that combine some of the best attributes of statistical pattern recognition and feedforward artificial neural networks. It is the neural network implementation of kernel discriminate

analysis, and was introduced by Donald Specht in the late 1980's. Conventional PNN is a three layers feed forward network including input layer, pattern layer and summation layer. The input layer contains M nodes to accept input feature vector. The pattern layer consists of K pools of

pattern nodes. The k th pool in the pattern layer contains N_k number of pattern nodes. Each node in the pattern layer is connected with every node in the input layer. The summation layer consists of K nodes, one node for each pool in the pattern layer. Pattern nodes of each k th summation node are connected to the corresponding k th summation node in the summation layer. Gaussian function is often chosen as the activation function, combined with a radial basis function in the pattern layer. For the summation layer, a linear basis function and a linear activation function is used. If there are N nodes in the pattern layer representing class A, the conventional PDF estimation for A is where G is the kernel function, d is dimension of input, and σ is the radius factor which is usually chosen by cross validation or by more esoteric methods. However, a single σ may not be always fit for all the patterns, particularly when the number of patterns is large. Hence, covariance matrix Σ corresponding to each pattern might be more suitable. On the other hand, standard PNN assumes that one pattern belongs to only one class. This property limits its usage for MR image classification, in which partial volume effect makes pattern contribute across classes.

A weighted PNN is developed to resolve these problems. The structure of WPNN is close to conventional PNN, except that weighting factors from soft labeling matrix, which can indicate the reference vectors' probabilities of belonging to final target classes, are introduced between pattern-to summation layer. Unlike PNN, whose weights are either 1 for connection going to the output that the node belongs to, or 0 for all other connections, the WPNN enable every unit in pattern layer contribute to output is the structure of the novel WPNN.

Methodology

A description of the derivation of the PNN classifier was given in Chettri and Crop. PNNs had been used for classification problems. The PNN classifier presented good accuracy, very small training time, robustness to weight changes, and negligible retraining time. There are 6 stages involved in the proposed model which are starting from the data input to output. The first stage is should be the image processing system. Basically in image processing system, image acquisition and image enhancement are the steps that have to do. In this paper, these two steps are skipped and all the images are collected from available resource. The proposed model requires converting the image into a format capable of being manipulated by the computer. The MR images are converted into matrices form by using MATLAB. Then, the PNN is used to classify the MR images. Lastly, performance based on the result will be analyzed at the end of the development phase.

In PNN algorithm, calculating the class-node activations is a simple process. For each class node, the example vector activations are summed, which are the sum of the products of the example vector and the input vector. The hidden node activation, shown in the following equation, is simply the product of the two vectors (E is the example vector, and F is the input feature vector).

$$H_i = E_i F \tag{5}$$

The class output activations are then defined as:

$$C_j = (\sum_{i=1}^N \exp(h_i - 1) / \gamma^2) / N \tag{6}$$

Where,

h- The hidden-node activation, and

γ - A smoothing factor.

The smoothing factor is chosen through experimentation. If the smoothing factor is too large, details can be lost, but if the smoothing factor is too small, the classifier may not generalize well

In this project, PNN has been implemented for classification of MR brain image. PNN is adopted for it has fast speed on training and simple structure. Twenty images of MR brain were used to train the PNN classifier and tests were run on different set of images to examine classifier accuracy. The developed classifier was examined under different spread values as a smoothing factor. Experimental result indicates that PNN classifier is workable with an accuracy ranged from 100% to 73% according to the spread value.

d) Spatial Fuzzy Clustering Method

Fuzzy C-means is an overlapping clustering technique. It is also called soft clustering method. One of the most widely used fuzzy clustering algorithms is the Fuzzy C-means algorithm. Fuzzy C-means segmentation is over hard segmentation method because they could retain much more information from the original image. Fuzzy C-means is a method of clustering which allows one piece of data to belong to two or more clusters. It works by assigning membership to each data point corresponding to each cluster center on the basis of distance between the cluster center and data point

The FCM algorithm is partition of n element $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ into a collection of c fuzzy clusters with respect to below given criteria.

It is based on minimization of the following objective function

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^m u_{ij}^m |x_i - y_j|^2$$

Where,

m = level of fuzziness and real number greater than 1.

u_{ij} = degree of membership of x_i in the cluster c_j

x = data value

Fuzzy C-means is a popular method for medical image. The segmentation performed by using spatial fuzzy C means clustering algorithm is an unsupervised clustering algorithm that classifies the input data points into multiple classes based on their inherent distance from each other. It includes the spatial function to modify membership function to get the accurate result by analyzing local neighbourhood information.

Algorithmic steps for Fuzzy c-means clustering

Fuzzy clustering is a powerful unsupervised method for the analysis of data and construction of models. In many situations, fuzzy clustering is more natural than hard clustering. Objects on the boundaries between several classes are not forced to fully belong to one of the classes, but rather are assigned membership degrees between 0 and 1 indicating their partial membership. Fuzzy c-means algorithm is most widely used. Fuzzy c-means clustering was first reported in the literature for a special case ($m=2$) by Joe Dunn in 1974. The general case (for any m greater than 1) was developed by Jim Bezdek in his PhD thesis at Cornell University in 1973. It can be improved by Bezdek in 1981. The FCM employs fuzzy partitioning such that a data point can belong to all groups with different membership grades between 0 and 1.

Algorithm

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots, x_n\}$ be the set of data points and $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3 \dots, v_c\}$ be the set of centers.

1) Randomly select ‘ c ’ cluster centers.

2) Calculate the fuzzy membership ‘ μ_{ij} ’ using:

$$\mu_{ij} = 1 / (\sum_{k=1}^c (d_{ij}/d_{ik})^{(2/m-1)}) \tag{8}$$

3) Compute the fuzzy centers ‘ v_j ’ using:

$$\gamma_j = (\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_{ij})^m x_i) / (\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_{ij})^m), \forall j=1, 2, \dots, c \tag{9}$$

4) Repeat step 2) and 3) until the minimum ‘ J ’ value is achieved or $||U^{(k+1)} - U^{(k)}|| < \beta$.

where, ‘ k ’ is the iteration step. ‘ β ’ is the termination criterion between [0, 1]. ‘ $U = (\mu_{ij})_{n \times c}$ ’ is the fuzzy membership matrix. ‘ J ’ is the objective function.

This algorithm works by assigning membership to each data point corresponding to each cluster center on the basis of distance between the cluster center and the data point. More the data is near to the cluster center more is its membership towards the particular cluster center. Clearly, summation of membership of each data point should be equal to one. After each iteration

Table 1. Comparison of Classifiers

Classifier	# of Correct Classified Samples	Correct Classification Rate
Hard C-Means	168	78.1%
Fuzzy C-Means	180	83.7%

Advantages

- 1) Unsupervised
- 2) Converges

e) Image Segmentation

The segmentation refers to the process of partitioning a digital image into multiple segments. The goal is to simplify and change the representation of an image into something that is more meaningful and easier to analyze. The segmentation is performed by using spatial fuzzy C means clustering algorithm. It is an unsupervised clustering algorithm that classifies the input data points into multiple classes based on their inherent distance from each other. It includes the spatial function to modify membership function to get the accurate result by analyzing local neighbourhood information.

Wavelet Transform

D Continuous Wavelet Transform

The 1-D continuous wavelet transform is given by:

$$W_f(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi_{a,b}(t) dt \tag{9}$$

The inverse 1-D wavelet transform is given by:

$$X(t) = \frac{1}{C} \int_0^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W_f(a, b) \psi_{a,b}(t) db \frac{da}{a^2} \tag{10}$$

$$\text{Where } C = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{|\Psi(\omega)|^2}{\omega} d\omega < \infty \tag{11}$$

$\Psi(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of the mother wavelet $\Psi(t)$. C is required to be finite, which leads to one of the required properties of a mother wavelet. Since C must be finite, then $\Psi(0) = 0$ to avoid a singularity in the integral, and thus the $\Psi(t)$ must have zero mean. This condition can be stated as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi(t) dt = 0 \quad (12)$$

and known as the admissibility condition.

D Discrete Wavelet Transform

The discrete wavelets transform (DWT), which transforms a discrete time signal to a discrete wavelet representation. The first step is to discretize the wavelet parameters, which reduce the previously continuous basis set of wavelets to a discrete and orthogonal / orthonormal set of basis wavelets.

$$\psi_{m,n}(t) = 2^{m/2} \psi(2^m t - n) \quad ; m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } -\infty < m, n < \infty \quad (13)$$

The 1-D DWT is given as the inner product of the signal $x(t)$ being transformed with each of the discrete basis functions.

$$W_{m,n} = \langle x(t), \psi_{m,n}(t) \rangle \quad ; m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (14)$$

The 1-D inverse DWT is given as:

$$x(t) = \sum_m \sum_n W_{m,n} \psi_{m,n}(t) \quad ; m, n \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (15)$$

D Wavelet Transform

The 1-D DWT can be extended to 2-D transform using separable wavelet filters. With separable filters, applying a 1-D transform to all the rows of the input and then repeating on all of the columns can compute the 2-D transform. When one-level 2-D DWT is applied to an image, four transform coefficient sets are created. As depicted in Figure 3.2(c), the four sets are LL, HL, LH, and HH, where the first letter corresponds to applying either a low pass or high pass filter to the rows, and the second letter refers to the filter applied to the columns.

Block Diagram of DWT (a) Original Image (b) Output image after the 1-D applied on Row input (c) Output image after the second 1-D applied on row input

The Two-Dimensional DWT (2D-DWT) converts images from spatial domain to frequency domain. At each level of the wavelet decomposition, each column of an image is first transformed using

vertical wavelet filter-bank. The same filter-bank is then applied horizontally to each row of the filtered and sub sampled data. One-level of wavelet decomposition produces four filtered and sub sampled images, referred to as sub bands. The upper and lower areas of Fig. 3.3(b), respectively, represent the low pass and high pass coefficients after vertical 1D-DWT and sub sampling. The result of the horizontal 1D-DWT and sub sampling to form a 2D-DWT output image is shown in Fig.3.3(c).

We can use multiple levels of wavelet transforms to concentrate data energy in the lowest sampled bands. Specifically, the LL sub band in fig 2.1(c) can be transformed again to form LL2, HL2, LH2, and HH2 sub bands, producing a two-level wavelet transform. An (R-1) level wavelet decomposition is associated with R resolution levels numbered from 0 to (R-1), with 0 and (R-1) corresponding to the coarsest and finest resolutions.

The straight forward convolution implementation of 1D-DWT requires a large amount of memory and large computation complexity. An alternative implementation of the 1D-DWT, known as the lifting scheme, provides significant reduction in the memory and the computation complexity. Lifting also allows in-place computation of the wavelet coefficients. Nevertheless, the lifting approach computes the same coefficients as the direct filter-bank convolution.

D Transform Heirarchy

The 1-D wavelet transform can be extended to a two-dimensional (2-D) wavelet transform using separable wavelet filters. With separable filters the 2-D transform can be computed by applying a 1-D transform to all the rows of the input, and then repeating on all of the columns.

Subband Labeling Scheme for a one level, 2-D Wavelet Transform

The original image of a one-level (K=1), 2-D wavelet transform, with corresponding notation is shown in Fig. 3.13. The example is repeated for a three-level (K =3) wavelet expansion in Fig. 3.14. In all of the discussion K represents the highest level of the decomposition of the wavelet transform.

LL ₁	HL ₁	HL ₂	HL ₃
LH ₁	HH ₁		
LH ₂		HH ₂	
LH ₃		HH ₃	

Subband labeling Scheme for a Three Level, 2-D Wavelet Transform

The 2-D subband decomposition is just an extension of 1-D subband decomposition. The entire process is carried out by executing 1-D subband decomposition twice, first in one direction (horizontal), then in the orthogonal (vertical) direction. For example, the low-pass subbands (Li) resulting from the horizontal direction is further decomposed in the vertical direction, leading to LLi and LHi subbands. Similarly, the high pass subband (Hi) is further decomposed into HLi and HHi. After one level of transform, the image can be further decomposed by applying the 2-D subband decomposition to the existing LLi subband. This iterative process results in multiple “transform levels”. In Fig. 3.14 the first level of transform results in LH1, HL1, and HH1, in addition to LL1, which is further decomposed into LH2, HL2, HH2, LL2 at the second level, and the information of LL2 is used for the third level transform. The subband LLi is a low-resolution subband and high-pass subbands LHi, HLi, HHi are horizontal, vertical, and diagonal subband respectively since they represent the horizontal, vertical, and diagonal residual information of the original image.

To obtain a two-dimensional wavelet transform, the one-dimensional transform is applied first along the rows and then along the columns to produce four subbands: low-resolution, horizontal, vertical, and diagonal. (The vertical subband is created by applying a horizontal high-pass, which yields vertical edges.) At each level, the wavelet transform can be reapplied to the low-resolution subband to further decorrelate the image. Fig. 3.16 illustrates the image decomposition, defining level and subband conventions used in the AWIC algorithm. The final configuration contains a small low-resolution subband. In addition to the various transform levels, the phrase level 0 is used to refer to the original image data.

Wavelet Computation

In order to obtain an efficient wavelet computation, it is important to eliminate as many unnecessary computations as possible. A careful examination of the forward and reverse transforms shows that about half the operations either lead to data which are destroyed or are null. The one-dimensional wavelet transform is computed by separately applying two analysis filters at alternating even and odd locations. The inverse process first doubles the length of each signal by inserting zeros in every other position, then applies the appropriate synthesis filter to each signal and adds the filtered signals to get the final reverse transform.

Step1: Column wise processing to get H and L

$H = (Co - Ce)$
 $L = (Ce + H/2)$

Where Co and Ce is the odd column and even column wise pixel values

Step 2: Row wise processing to get LL,LH,HL and HH,

Separate odd and even rows of H and L,
 Namely, Hodd – odd row of H, Lodd- odd row of L, Heven- even row of H
 Leven – even row of L
 LH = Lodd-Leven
 LL = Leven + (LH / 2)
 HH = Hodd – Heven
 HL = Heven + (HH / 2)

DecompositionalFlow

Fig: Decompositional Flow

Reverse Lifting scheme in IWT

Inverse Integer wavelet transform is formed by Reverse lifting scheme. Procedure is similar to the forward lifting scheme for each direction, giving a total of four GLCMs. From each GLCM, the four features contrast, correlation, energy, and homogeneity were calculated, in total 16 texture features per concatenated image. As a comparison, isotropic GLCMs, matrices consisting of the average of the GLCMs for the four directions, were constructed. The four features calculated from this matrix were then used as explanatory variables in the SVM classification

The proposed method consists of Training samples of both the normal and abnormal condition of brain tumor images. With the help of these samples, PNN network is trained. Initially training samples are decomposed into low and high frequency bands, from that decomposed image texture features like contrast, Correlation, energy and homogeneity were extracted, from these feature values neural network is trained. The feature values are varied for normal and abnormal condition images. The different feature values are given to the network for training purpose.

Once training phase is completed, next the classification phase (Testing Phase) is performed. Here the training samples are given to the network, then it can be decomposed into different bands using dual tree complex wavelet transform. After that different texture features are extracted from the testing samples. These features are given to the PNN network. Already in training phase different features are extracted and stored. Here target values are fixed for normal and abnormal condition images. For normal image target will be one and for abnormal image target will be two. Now both the training and testing vector features are compared. If the difference is one or below than one it will be a normal condition image, if the difference is more than one or two then it will be a

Abnormal image. Based on these results, segmentation is carried out. If the classification result is Normal then no need to use segmentation process. If the result is abnormal then segmentation process is used. For segmentation process spatial fuzzy clustering method is used. In this segmentation process the exact brain tumor part is detected. In medical applications it will be more helpful for early stage diagnosis. The main advantage is reduction in time and early diagnosis.

The following images were taken for the analysis of brain tumor as a training images

III. RESULTS

In medical diagnostic systems, fuzzy c-means algorithm gives the better results than hard-k-means algorithm. Fuzzy clustering methods can be important supportive tool for the medical experts in diagnostic. Results obtained from the training sample images by texture analysis of considering the four GLCM characteristics and find the area affected by tumor in the brain region. The performance of the MRI brain image classification approach was evaluated in terms of training performance and classification accuracies. The simulated results will be shown that classifier and segmentation algorithm provides better accuracy than previous method.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. N. Harry, F. J. Gilhert, and D. E. Parkin, "Predicting the response of advanced cervical and ovarian tumors to therapy," *Obstetr. Gynecol. Surv.*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 548–560, Aug. 2009.
- [2] L. Alic, M. van Vliet, C. F. van Dijke, A. M. M. Eggermont, J. F. Veenland, and W. J. Niessen, "Heterogeneity in DCE-MRI parametric maps: A biomarker for treatment response?," *Phys. Med. Biol.*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 1601–1616, Mar. 2011.
- [3] H. Lyng, A. O. Vorren, K. Sundfor, I. Taksdal, H. H. Lien, A. Kaalhus, and E. K. Rofstad, "Assessment of tumor oxygenation in human cervical carcinoma by use of dynamic Gd-DTPA-enhanced MR imaging," *J. Magn. Reson. Imag.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 750–756, Dec. 2001.
- [4] M. A. Zahra, K. G. Hollingsworth, E. Sala, D. J. Lomas, and L. T. Tan, "Dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI as a predictor of tumour response to radiotherapy," *Lancet Oncol.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 63–74, Jan. 2007.
- [5] R. C. Gonzalez and R. E. Woods, *Digital Image Processing*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson/Prentice Hall, 2008.
- [6] M. Mirmehdi, X. Xie, and J. Suri, *Handbook of Texture Analysis*. London, U.K.: Imperial College Press, 2008.

V. Knopp, "Quantifying tumor vascular heterogeneity with dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging: A review," *J. Biomed. Biotechnol.*, p. 12, Feb. 2011.

[8] S. C. Agner, S. Soman, E. Libfeld, M. McDonald, K. Thomas, S. Englander, M. A. Rosen, D. Chin, J. Noshier, and A. Madabhushi, "Textural kinetics: A novel dynamic contrast-enhanced (DCE)-MRI feature for breast lesion classification," *J. Digital Imag.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 446–463, Jun. 2011.

[9] M. E. Mayerhoefer, P. Szomolanyi, D. Jirak, A. Materka, and S. Trattnig, "Effects of MRI acquisition parameter variations and protocol heterogeneity on the results of texture analysis and pattern discrimination: An application-oriented study," *Med. Phys.*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 1236–1243, Apr. 2009.

[10] G. Castellano, L. Bonilha, L. M. Li, and F. Cendes, "Texture analysis of medical images," *Clinical Radiology*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 1061–1069, Dec. 2004.

[11] L. Alic, "Quantification of tumour heterogeneity in MRI," Ph.D. dissertation, Dept. Med. Informat., Erasmus Univ., Rotterdam, The Netherlands, 2013.

[12] A. Karahaliou, K. Vassiou, N. S. Arikidis, S. Skiadopoulos, T. Kanavou, and L. Costaridou, "Assessing heterogeneity of lesion enhancement kinetics in dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI for breast cancer diagnosis," *Br. J. Radiol.*, vol. 83, no. 988, pp. 296–306, Apr. 2010.

[13] C. Halle, E. Andersen, M. Lando, E. K. Aarnes, G. Hasvold, M. Holden, R. G. Syljuasen, K. Sundfor, G. B. Kristensen, R. Holm, E. Malinen, and H. Lyng, "Hypoxia-induced gene expression in chemoradioresistant cervical cancer revealed by dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI," *Cancer Res.*, vol. 72, Oct. 2012.

[14] E. K. F. Andersen, K. H. Hole, K. V. Lund, K. Sundfor, G. B. Kristensen, H. Lyng, and E. Malinen, "Dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI of cervical cancers: Temporal percentile screening of contrast enhancement identifies parameters for prediction of chemoradioresistance," *Int. J. Radiat. Oncol. Biol. Phys.*, vol. 82, Mar. 2012.

[15] E. K. F. Andersen, K. H. Hole, K. V. Lund, K. Sundfor, G. B. Kristensen, H. Lyng, and E. Malinen, "Pharmacokinetic parameters derived from dynamic contrast enhanced MRI of cervical cancers predict chemoradiotherapy outcome," *Radiother. Oncol.*, vol. 107, Apr. 2013.

[16] L. Alic, "Quantification of tumour heterogeneity in MRI," Ph.D. dissertation, Dept. Med. Informat., Erasmus Univ., Rotterdam, The Netherlands, 2013.

[17] L. Alic, M. van Vliet, C. F. van Dijke, A. M. M. Eggermont, J. F. Veenland, and W. J. Niessen, "Heterogeneity in DCE-MRI parametric maps: a biomarker for treatment response?," *Physics in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 56, Mar. 2011.

[18] Mamta Bharadwaj, Ankita Walia, Hemant Tulsani, || *Comparative Research on Fuzzy C-Means and K-Means Clustering Segmentation*, —International Journal of Computer Applications & Information Technology Vol. 3, Issue II Aug-September 2013.

[19] P. Dhanalakshmi & T. Kanimozhi, "Automatic Segmentation of Brain Tumor using K-Means Clustering and its Area Calculation", International Journal of Advanced Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IJAEEL), Volume-2, Issue-2, 2013.

[20] S.J. Wang and R.M. Summers, "Machine learning and radiology," *Med. Image Anal.*, vol. 16, Jul. 2012.

[21] Probabilistic neural network for brain tumor classification by Mohd fauzi Othman and mohd Ariffanam mohd Basri, second internal conference intelligent systems, modeling and simulation, 2011.